

Flammable Gas Mixture Test Fixture Standardizations

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Abstract—Lightning strike and static electricity ignition hazard testing for aircraft typically follow one of two test methods per SAE ARP5416A. These two methods detect the presence of an ignition hazard through either (1) the combustion of a flammable gas mixture ignitable by a 200 microJoule (μJ) voltage arc or (2) light emission greater than that of a 200 μJ voltage arc. The instrumentation and test conditions of the voltage arc source is not fully constrained by industry standards which could lead to overly conservative or erroneous results when performing ignition hazard testing and thus cause costlier or ineffective remediations and designs for EME protection. Understanding the sensitivities of the two test methods to different parameters that affect the optical and incandescence properties of the arc is the main goal of this paper. Such parameters include the spacing of the electrode, varying the temporal waveform, and identifying the effects of the ambient humidity. Additionally, we provide recommendations on characterizing the voltage arc energy with temporal current and voltage measurement combined with numerical simulations and analysis of parasitic impedances. We also give potential alternative methods for verifying the ignitability of the flammable gas mixture and provide an equipment design for the flammable gas mixture test method. In order to deliver these results, two phases of testing are conducted with the aforementioned variables using the Boeing Company patented fixture, Patent Number 10,620,179 (Systems and Methods for Non-Flammable Indication of Incandescence) and Number 10,738,754 (Rapid Sample Ignition Test System). We then explore the use of the partial pressures alternative by exploring the sensitivity of the flammable gas to partial pressures. This method is discussed in greater detail in the draft of the upcoming Revision B of SAE ARP5416.

Keywords— Ignition testing, voltage arc source, flammable gas mixture, partial pressures

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to protect an aircraft from lightning and static electricity, several tests must be conducted to ensure the aircraft meets regulations. One such test is ignition testing, a lightning direct effects test, which investigates whether an ignition hazard occurs. An ignition hazard can occur when sufficient ignition sources exist within a flammable environment. Without proper protection, when the ignition sources are energized at an interface, the ignition sources ignite the flammable environment, causing a pressure and temperature rise. This ignition can lead to catastrophic failure such as flames, fire, structural damage, and possible explosion. Thus, when

performing ignition testing, the main objective is to show that ignition sources are not sufficient enough to ignite for the test specimen.

Revision A of SAE ARP5416 (*Aircraft Lightning Test Methods*) outlines two test methods for detecting ignition sources: an optical method, and an ignitable mixture (flammable gas) test method [1]. The upcoming draft, Revision B, of SAE ARP5416, discusses the flammable gas test method in further detail, and both documents define criteria and standards to use for the test methods [2].

The optical method utilizes a camera capable of detecting a 200 μJ voltage arc to take images of test objects during lightning testing. The camera and test article are placed in a dark, closed out environment; when lightning current is applied to the test article, the camera will take images, and if light appears in an image, then an ignition has occurred.

In contrast, the flammable gas test method uses a flammable gas mixture ignitable by a 200 μJ voltage arc source and applies energy to a test specimen within the flammable environment. Throughout the test, the pressure and temperature within the test chamber are monitored, and if during the test there is a spike in the pressure and temperature, then ignition has occurred.

- Two different methods for creating a flammable mixture are
- Using mass flow controllers to control the flow rate of each gas based on the stoichiometry from the combustion equation.
 - Using partial pressures of the gases and fill the volume adding each gas to the system until a certain pressure based on the stoichiometry is reached on the pressure gauge.

The main focus of this paper is to understand the sensitivities of the optical and flammable gas methods to different parameters, namely discharge energy and gap distance. Although there is criteria for the different parameters outlined within industry standards for the flammable gas testing, we wanted to better characterize the voltage arc energy and provide equipment design. In the following sections, we summarize the testing procedure and equipment, discuss the test results and analysis, compare with our models and simulations, and provide closing remarks.

II. TEST SETUP

A Standard Operating Procedure was written and reviewed before performing any tests using the flammable gas mixture test fixture. Testing is broken down into two different phases: the first phase characterizes the light output and discharge current waveform of the voltage arc source, while the second phase studies the propensity of varying the equivalence ratio of the gas.

A. Phase 1 Testing: Characterizing the Sparker

For the first phase of testing, no flammable gas is used. Instead, the light emission and discharge current waveform of the voltage arc source is characterized by varying the discharge energy and the gap distance, as shown in the test matrix in Table I.

In order to understand the sensitivities of the sparker to these parameters, images are taken when sparks occur and are compared to the predicted discharge energy. The camera shutter is open for the full duration of each arc discharge. The current waveforms for each spark are also captured, and the discharge energy (U) is again calculated and compared with the previous calculations and the images.

1) Equipment Setup:

The flammable gas mixture test fixture consists of two verification chambers that each house a voltage arc source, or “sparker”. These voltage arc sources create a tunable energy discharge. Figure 1 illustrates the composition of the verification chambers. The upper and lower chambers each contain a voltage arc source that creates a tuneable energy discharge. Dry, compressed air can be added to the chamber, which lowers the humidity and cleans the sparker. The compressed air can also be used for purging the system, although it is recommended to use nitrogen for purging the system instead of compressed air. The high voltage comes into the chamber through a porcelain feedthrough and is connected to the circuit within the sparker. The voltage can then be tuned at the input of the high voltage source. Similarly, the capacitance within the voltage arc source can be tuned; tuning both the voltage and capacitance is vital to reach the desired energy discharge threshold. Figure 2 shows a circuit diagram of the voltage arc source.

Fig. 1 A simplified diagram of the upper and lower chamber configurations containing the voltage arc sources.

Fig. 2 A diagram of the circuit within the voltage arc source, or sparker.

For this phase of testing, the front and back flange faces of the voltage arc source chamber are removed to expose the sparker. From there, a camera is set up on a raised platform behind the chamber and pointed at the sparker. An LCR meter is set up next to the chamber to test the capacitance across the electrodes, which is assumed to be the same capacitance within the voltage arc source circuit. A Pearson current probe is added to the circuit below the low voltage side electrode as shown in Figure 2. The current waveform is recorded on a DPO oscilloscope at 10^{10} samples/sec; the detection of a spark by the oscilloscope triggered the control sequence to save images, current traces, and reset the camera and oscilloscope for the next spark. A voltage probe is connected to the high voltage feedthrough as shown in Figure 2 and connected to a multimeter; the voltage reading from the multimeter is used to tune the voltage output of the power supply. Figure 3 shows a photo of the test setup used.

Fig. 3 A photo of the open verification chamber with the current probe connected to the voltage arc source circuit.

2) Test Procedure:

The test matrix rows are in a randomized order to ensure that any variability that could come from day-to-day testing is limited. The voltage arc source is conditioned by flowing dry air through the system into the chamber. Using the compressed air throughout the testing cycle ensures that the humidity within

the chamber is relatively constant, and when not in use, the front and back faces of the chambers are covered. The back of the chamber, which the camera faces, is covered with a transparent material to allow optical access to the arc source. Without these steps, the humidity within the chamber would allow charge to bleed through the air, resulting in inconsistent discharges.

The voltage arc source gap distance is set to the target gap using a calibrated feeler gauge. Then, the chamber face cover is added and the high voltage power supply is turned on. With the power supply on, the voltage is tuned until it reaches the breakdown voltage calculated from the targeted discharge energy. The actual voltage is then recorded, and the high voltage power supply is turned off and a grounding procedure is used. In order to maintain a reasonable amount of time between discharges, we target a discharge period greater than 5τ ; we calculated this target tau by using

$$\tau = RC \quad (1)$$

where τ is the discharge period in seconds, R is the resistance, and C is the capacitance.

Next, the capacitance within the voltage arc source circuit is tuned. The high voltage power supply is unplugged from the voltage arc source to prevent parasitic impedance in the reading. The probes of the LCR meter are placed on each side of the electrode. The target capacitance, C_{target} is calculated with

$$C_{\text{target}} = \frac{2U}{V^2} \quad (2)$$

where U is the target energy and V is the voltage output of the power supply. The variable capacitor is dialed as close as possible to C_{target} and the actual capacitance is recorded. The voltage arc source is placed back inside the chamber and the capacitance is once again confirmed before removing the LCR meter probes and reattaching the high voltage power supply. The chamber is closed off, and black-out fabric is used to cover the entire fixture, including the camera. The high voltage power supply and data acquisition code are left on for at least an hour.

4) Test Matrix:

The test matrix for Phase 1 testing is summarized in Table I. The independent variables are the discharge energy and the electrode spacing. In order to calculate the breakdown voltage and capacitance required to obtain the target discharge energy, the following equations were used. The breakdown voltage can be calculated using Paschen's law, in which

$$V_B = \frac{Bpd}{\ln(A'pd)} \quad (3)$$

where A' is a constant $0.29 \text{ 1}/(\text{mmTorr})$, p is 760 Pa , B is $38 \text{ V}/(\text{mmTorr})$, and d is the electrode gap distance [5]. For phase 1 testing, the voltage on the power supply was assumed to be the same as the breakdown voltage, and the power supply voltage was measured and tuned to a target value based on the electrode spacing. This assumption is supported by letting ensuring that the time between discharges is greater than 5τ ,

resulting in a maximum of 0.7% difference between the V_C and V_B . After tuning the breakdown voltage, the target capacitance is calculated using Equation 2 and the variable capacitor within the voltage arc source is tuned and the actual capacitance is recorded. The actual energy is then calculated from the measured voltage and capacitance values.

TABLE I
TEST MATRIX--PHASE 1 OF TESTING

Test ID	Target Discharge Energy (μJ)	Target Electrode Spacing (mm)
1-1	100	0.5
1-2	100	1.0
1-3	100	1.5
1-4	100	2.0
1-5	200	0.5
1-6	200	1.0
1-7	200	1.5
1-8	200	2.0
1-9	300	0.5
1-10	300	1.0
1-11	300	1.5
1-12	300	2.0
1-13	400	0.5
1-14	400	1.0
1-15	400	1.5
1-16	400	2.0

B. Phase 2 Testing: Flammable Gas Procedure

In this section, we describe the general flammable gas test procedure as prescribed by guidance from the draft of SAE ARP5416 (Revision B).

1) Equipment Setup:

Plumbing, pumps, and remote controlled valves allow for controlled gas flow into and out of the two chambers. Mass flow controllers and pressure transducers allow for accurate mixture ratio. A test chamber can be added in series between the verification chambers. Figure 4 illustrates the basic plumbing of the fixture and where a test chamber can be installed.

Fig. 4 A simplified diagram of the flammable gas fixture, including a test chamber in series between the two verification chambers. A larger version of the figure can be found in A-1.

The flammable gas mixture test fixture is set on top of a mobile optical table and is moved under the vent hood during operation in order to ensure proper ventilation. The different gases – nitrogen, oxygen, and ethylene – enter the test apparatus through mass flow controllers, or can be bypassed using valves in parallel with the mass flow controllers.

There are a few manual valves on the fixture, but primarily, the system is composed of remote valves that can be opened and closed from a separate control room. Before testing, the remote valves operation is verified. While using any of the flammable gases, two gas detectors are used: one is left in the testing area, and the other is kept on the test operator at all times. Three oscilloscopes are used during the tests and are accessed through the remote computer. These oscilloscopes provide data on the current waveforms and if a pressure rise has occurred in the second phase of testing.

At the start of a new testing cycle, the flammable gas mixture test fixture on its optical table is wheeled near the fume hood to aid in ventilation and connected to the main controls. If the partial pressure method is being used, the vacuum pump is connected to the plumbing and placed on an immobilized surface. The oil levels of the vacuum pump are checked and refilled if necessary. For the mass flow controller method, each gas line uses a mass flow controller and is set to the proper flow rate based on the desired equivalence ratio.

If it is applicable, a test chamber is connected to the ignition fixture, between the upper and lower sparker chambers. For the purposes of this paper, no test chamber is used, and the upper and lower chambers are connected directly via tubing. Then, the flexible gas supply and exhaust lines are connected.

The next step is to tune and calibrate the sparkers. To begin, the front flange of the upper and lower chambers are removed, and the electrode tips are cleaned and the gap between the electrodes is set to 1.5 mm. The sparker is then tested to ensure that the voltage arc source is producing discharges according to the stored energy values in Table II by tuning the voltage to the breakdown voltages found in Phase 1 of testing. Based on this breakdown voltage and the desired energy, the capacitance can be calculated and the variable capacitor within the voltage arc source can be tuned to the target capacitance value. The front flanges are replaced and the chambers are dried by continuously running for an hour with the dry air valves open, or pulling a vacuum on the system first and backfilling with nitrogen while allowing the voltage arc source to spark.

2) Creating an Accurate Gas Mixture:

The gas calibration procedures differ between the mass flow controller method and the partial pressures method. The gas mixture used is an ethylene, oxygen, and nitrogen mixture. The combustion equation of an ethylene-air mixture is

where ϕ is the equivalence ratio of ethylene to oxygen.

By using the combustion reaction of these gases, we can substitute the desired equivalence ratio in to the reactants and calculate the concentration of each gas is needed. This equation for calculating the concentration of ethylene is shown by

$$X_{C_2H_4} = \frac{\phi}{\phi + 3(1 + 3.76)} \quad (5)$$

where $X_{C_2H_4}$ is the concentration of ethylene and the denominator is the sum of the reactant coefficients in the combustion equation.

For the mass flow controller method, the concentration of the individual gas is multiplied by the total volume of the system in liters to find the flow of gases per minute. This is done using

$$m_{f_{ethylene}} = X_{C_2H_4} V_{tot} \quad (6)$$

with $m_{f_{ethylene}}$ being the mass flow rate in SLPM for ethylene and V_{tot} being the total system volume in liters [2].

In the partial pressures method, instead of multiplying by the total system volume, the percentage of the individual gas is multiplied by the total pressure of the chamber as shown by

$$P_{ethylene} = X_{C_2H_4} P_{tot} \quad (7)$$

where $P_{ethylene}$ is the partial pressure of ethylene in psi and P_{tot} is the total system pressure in psi.

For example, the ethylene concentration required for an equivalence ratio of 0.6 is calculated to be 0.4032. Then, using the mass flow controller method, 0.4032 is multiplied by the total volume in liters, which in our case is about 17 liters. This yields an ethylene flow rate of 0.686 SLPM. Faster flow rates can be used, but for simplicity we perform five overall volume changes within 5 minutes. Using the partial pressures method, 0.4032 multiplied by the chamber pressure, which at atmospheric is 14.7 psi, to yield 0.593 psi.

3) Test Procedure:

For this test, the electrode spacing was kept constant at 1.5 mm, and instead of varying the gap distance, our two main test variables are the target discharge energy and the equivalence ratio of ethylene. The primary objective of the second phase of testing is to add to the existing data on equivalence ratio versus ignition energy as shown in Figure 5. When varying the equivalence ratio and ignition energies, we expect to see that test data points that fall above the curve will ignite, while test points below the curve will fail to ignite.

Fig. 5 Minimum Ignition Energy of Ethylene-Air Mixture, adapted from Figure 40 in SAE ARP 5416 Rev B [2].

Before filling the chambers with flammable gases, it is first important to ensure that the voltage arc source will work properly. The voltage is tuned to achieve dielectric breakdown with a discharge period greater than 5τ for a 1.5 mm gap, and the variable capacitor is tuned per section 8.7.2 of SAE ARP5416 REV B. Once the voltage arc source is properly tuned, the flange face is installed on the chamber.

The testing and results reported herein use the mass flow controller method. The gas flow rates are set remotely to the desired flow rates based off the equivalence ratio of the test, calculated using Equations 4-6. The remote valves are opened first to flow nitrogen through the system. After verifying the flow rate is correct with the nitrogen line's flow meter, the oxygen line is opened next, followed by the ethylene line. Nitrogen is used as a diluent; without sufficient nitrogen, the combustion reaction is more likely to detonate, burning hotter and faster [2]. The gases are allowed to run through the system enough to displace five total volumes, and since the flow rate is calculated to be in terms of per minute, it takes approximately five minutes to flow through. The gas lines are closed and the chambers are sealed off. Then, the voltage arc source is allowed to spark. Both oscilloscopes are accessed remotely; one is monitored for a spike in current, which signifies that a spark occurred. The other oscilloscope monitors and records the pressure waveform as voltage reading from the pressure gauges. The temperature is also monitored, however, for the purposes of this experiment, only the pressure rise waveform is recorded and converted from volts to psi. Once the voltage arc source sparks, the high voltage power supply is turned off. If there is a pressure rise, then an ignition has occurred. If there is no ignition after testing with 5 sparks, no ignition has occurred for the flammable mixture. In order to ensure that the gas mixture is indeed flammable, a glow plug connected to the chamber is used.

4) Test Matrix:

Table II shows the test matrix for the second phase of testing. The primary test variables are the target discharge energy and the equivalence ratio of ethylene. The discharge energy is set to either 200, 300, or 400 μJ , and the equivalence ratio of ethylene is set to 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, or 1.8. The electrode gap size was maintained at 1.5 mm. Using these values, the breakdown voltage, capacitance, and standard liters per minutes (SLPM; used for mass flow controller method) were calculated and used for the test.

TABLE II
TEST MATRIX – PHASE 2 OF TESTING

Test ID	Target Discharge Energy (μJ)	Equivalence Ratio of Ethylene
2-1	200	0.6
2-2	200	0.8
2-3	200	1.0
2-4	200	1.2
2-5	200	1.4
2-6	200	1.6

2-7	200	1.8
2-8	300	0.6
2-9	300	0.8
2-10	300	1.0
2-11	300	1.2
2-12	300	1.4
2-13	300	1.6
2-14	300	1.8
2-15	400	0.6
2-16	400	0.8
2-17	400	1.0
2-18	400	1.2
2-19	400	1.4
2-20	400	1.6
2-21	400	1.8

III. TEST RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The main focus when post-processing Phase 1 results is to understand the discharge characteristics and the images captured for each combination of arc gap and discharge energy. We examine the effects of varying the energy and gap distance, as well as other potential sources of error that could influence the results. For Phase 2 post-processing, the main area of interest is comparing the results to historical and theoretical values to add to industry data and grow confidence in mixture control methodologies.

Fig. 6 The RGB sum of camera pixels for each test. A larger version of the figure can be found in Fig A-2. Each image is the average of at least 50 discharge images for each configuration.

Humidity played a key role in whether the voltage arc source would spark for both test phases. On less humid days, the sparker would work consistently, but on very humid days, the voltage arc source would not work as anticipated. Using the vacuum pump to remove humid air from the system and then pumping through with nitrogen to repressurize the system became a key step to ensure the voltage arc source would operate correctly.

A. Phase 1 Results

The Phase 1 images are cropped and analyzed to compare the RGB sum values of each camera pixel with the actual energy and electrode spacing value, using the equation:

$$P_{\text{sum}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M (P_R + P_G + P_B)}{M} - N_{\text{avg}} \quad (8)$$

where P_{sum} is the RGB sum, M is the number of total images for a configuration, P_R are the red pixels, P_G are the green pixels, P_B are the blue pixels, and N_{avg} is the average noise of the dark region of the image. N_{avg} is subtracted due to the different shutter times when each image is captured.

The RGB pixel for each test configuration is plotted in Figure 6. Images with a longer exposure time tend to have more noise in the resulting RGB sum plot. The images with the highest RGB sum values have smaller electrode gaps and are tested at higher energy levels.

The maximum P_{sum} for a given image, P_{max} are calculated. The average and standard deviation of P_{max} for each configuration is plotted against their respective stored energy.

Figure 7 illustrates this relation. Seemingly, the maximum RGB pixel sum value does not increase with energy as expected when compared with a round robin test on camera calibration [7]. Revision B of SAE ARP5416 specifies that a “5 pixel minimum and preferably 10 pixels or greater spatial resolution of the standard voltage arc source gap (1.5 mm) is required” [2]. However, the image resolution used in our testing is much higher than this requirement with an average resolution of 84 ± 15 pixels/mm, leading to 42 to 168 pixels resolving the voltage arc. When comparing these results to historical data from a round robin series of testing in 2018, it appears that the historical test data used cameras with lower resolution and compared the peak pixel values [7]. To understand the effect of the camera resolution, we resampled the images with resolutions of 2.5 pixel/mm, 5.0 pixel/mm, 10 pixel/mm, 20 pixel/mm, and 40 pixel/mm and compared the relative maximum pixel RGB values as shown in Figure 8. When sampled at lower resolutions, it is easier to distinguish between different arc energies for most of the gap distances.

Fig. 7 The plot shows the maximum RGB pixel sum values for each test plotted against their stored energy in microJoules.

Fig. 8 Each subplot shows the maximum RGB pixel value against the stored capacitor energy value. The data within the subplots is separated by electrode gap length.

Figure 9 illustrates the average waveform from all discharges from a given configuration. Each discharge waveform within a configuration remains relatively consistent with one another and the maximum relative uncertainty for these waveforms is 8%. When analyzing the Phase 1 current waveform data from all discharges for the different configurations, we discover that there is a greater charge transfer than what is stored in the capacitor for larger electrode gaps. The equations for calculating the charge of the capacitor and the total charge transferred are as follows

$$Q_{cap} = CV \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{transfer} = \int i(t)dt \quad (11)$$

where Q_{cap} is the charge of the capacitor, $Q_{transfer}$ is the total charge transferred, and $i(t)$ is the momentary current at time t .

Fig. 9 Phase 1 testing results with the average waveform of all discharges for each configuration. A larger version of this figure can be found in Fig A-3.

Figure 10 shows the relationship between these two charges; we can observe that as the gap size increases, there is a greater charge transfer than the charge stored on the capacitor. Since there is a greater charge transfer observed in the current waveform than what is stored on the tuneable capacitor, the prevailing hypothesis is that there is a parasitic capacitance within the system that contributed to the charge transfer.

Fig. 10 Phase 1 testing results showing that the average charge stored on the capacitor is less than the average charge transfer.

We first investigate whether there is parasitic capacitance from the electrodes, since the larger gap distance data seemed to have a larger charge transfer. Electrostatic finite element models of voltage arc source electrodes found the capacitance will decrease as the gap spacing increases and was on a 0.3 to 0.4 pF scale. While this parasitic impedance is not insignificant to the overall capacitance, it trends increase for small gaps, which does not explain the observed result.

We then examine the parasitic resistance in the 300 GΩ charging resistor. If there is a significant parasitic capacitance in parallel with this resistor, then the high frequency content of the discharge could allow current to flow through the arc from the high voltage power supply. The impedance of a 300 GΩ resistor identical to the one used in the voltage arc source circuit is measured up to 300 kHz. This measurement gave a parasitic parallel capacitance of 0.446 ± 0.008 pF. Figure 11 shows the resulting current through this parasitic capacitance

calculated at 90 MHz, the most abundant frequency of the discharge.

Figure 11 illustrates the possible current provided by the 400 VA power supply and the current through the parasitic capacitance against the power supply voltage. This result shows that as the voltage is increased, the current allowed through the parasitic capacitance increases and could have a significant contribution to the total discharge current compared to Figure 9. This effect is limited by the power outputs and circuitry of the high voltage power supply. For future testing, we can fix this issue by replacing the high voltage power supply that is current limited to be much lower than the discharge current.

Fig. 11 Current based on parasitic capacitance compared to the power supply voltage in kV.

B. Phase 2 Results

Figure 12 shows the test results on the same plot as the literature data for ethylene/air ignitions. Historical data indicates that discharge energies falling above the curve from literature data consistently ignite the ethylene-oxygen mixture for a given equivalence ratio. Generally, our data follows this trend. While this data at first glance does not look like it meets expected results for three of the data points, when taking into account the equivalence ratio calculation uncertainty from the mass flow controller readings, two of the three data points cross the literature data curve. Only the result at an equivalence ratio of 1.6 and energy discharge of 300 microJoules did not meet the expected result. However, given the overall statistical nature of spark ignition, which was not reported in previous publications, these results are consistent [8].

Fig. 12 Minimum Ignition Energy of Ethylene-Air Mixture, adapted from Figure 40 in SAE ARP 5416 Rev B with results from Phase 2 Testing conducted in June 2024.

Fig. 13 Phase 2 testing results showing the equivalence ratio versus the maximum pressure in psi measured.

Fig. 14 This plot illustrates the theoretical maximum pressure without losses in psi versus the equivalence ratio, plotted with the experimental results.

The theoretical maximum pressure is modeled using the GRI3.0 thermodynamic mechanism of a constant volume explosion in Cantera [8,9]. Figure 13 illustrates the equivalence

ratio plotted against the maximum pressure for measurement. Figure 14 shows both the measured maximum pressures and the theoretical maximum pressure from the simulation plotted with the values in psi. While the magnitude between the test points and the theoretical pressure curve is different due to losses, the shape of the data follows the same trend as the curve, resulting in increased confidence that the target equivalence ratios were achieved. Although there should be a difference between the theoretical and results due to losses, the losses should not cause as significant of a difference as what is seen in Figure 14. Potential factors that could influence this difference are a faulty pressure transducer, the gas mixture containing extra diluent (nitrogen), or the mixture not being mixed well enough. Using the partial pressures method instead of the mass flow controllers could help produce more accurate equivalence ratios. Comparing the uncertainties of the equivalence ratios for the two methods, the relative uncertainties using the partial pressure method are approximately 0.4-1.0% for a HPO series Heise gauge, while the relative uncertainties using the mass flow controllers used in this testing are approximately 2.7-16.5% for our range of equivalence ratios.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Both phases of testing were conducted successfully in Charleston, SC. In Phase 1 of testing, we explored the sensitivities and the optical properties of the voltage arc source by varying the target discharge energy and the electrode gap spacing. Through post-processing of the captured photos and comparing with the energy and gap size, we determined that while the total RGB pixel sum values showed a difference between different energies, there was little difference between the maximum RGB pixel sum values for different discharge energy levels. Only when the resolution of the photos was reduced was there a noticeable difference in the maximum RGB sum values. Therefore care should be taken to tune the resolution of the camera appropriately to capture potential ignition sources when following ARP5416 guidance.

Analyzing the current waveforms from the first phase of testing led to the discovery that the total charge transfer was greater than the total charge stored on the capacitor within the voltage arc source. Analysis of the impedances show that this is likely due to parasitic capacitance in parallel with the charging resistor. This results in a greater energy arc than what the voltage arc source is tuned to which would result in an unconservative calibration of a flammable mixture or camera. Care should be taken with specific charging circuits to identify parasitics and ensure that they result in a conservative voltage arc.

In Phase 2, the main objectives were to understand the incandive properties of the arc and to add to the minimum ignition energy data set for ethylene. The target discharge energy and the equivalence ratio of ethylene to oxygen were the independent variables tested.

The results from the second phase of testing were compared to historical data for ethylene. Almost all test configurations fell within the curve generated from historical data, however, there were three points that did not yield what was expected. Two of

these points were on the fuel-rich side of the curve, where there was less historical data available.

When plotting the equivalence ratio against the maximum pressure, the trend follows the curve modeling the theoretical maximum pressure for ethylene without any losses at different equivalence ratios. Given the overall statistical nature of spark ignition, this result is in line with literature [8].

Several improvements could be made for future testing. Humidity proved to be a critical factor in whether the voltage arc source would spark from day-to-day; measuring and testing the effects of humidity could be a potential avenue for subsequent experimentation with the flammable gas fixture. Another improvement could be replacing the high voltage power supply with a power supply that is more current limiting. Using the partial pressures method instead of the mass flow controller method could also largely improve test results as well as it can better quantify the leak rate and ensure that the flammable gas mixture is accurate. Identifying ways to limit and/or eliminate sources of energy loss such as circuit losses, residual capacitor energy, and electromagnetic radiation could also provide more robust results [6].

Our observations show that the light intensity observed through open shutter imaging does not correlate with the discharge energy when the arc is well resolved. Additionally, analysis of the current waveforms shows discrepancies in the charge transfer in the charge stored on the capacitor, which translates to discrepancies in expected and actual discharge energy. However, when using a flammable gas mixture with an accurate equivalence ratio, ignition of the gas with a voltage arc source with a given energy reliably ignites the mixture. Therefore, industry testing may be more repeatable if ignitability standards are based on mixture composition and not reliance on an inconsistent voltage arc source.

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APPENDIX: HIGH RESOLUTION FIGURES

Fig A-1. High resolution of the plumbing diagram found in Fig. 4

Fig A-2. High resolution version of RGB Sum diagram found in Fig. 6

Fig A-3. High resolution version of average waveforms diagram found in Fig. 9